

DYNAMICS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND ITS CLINICAL CONSEQUENCES

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Annotation: The liver is a vital organ that performs numerous essential functions in the human body. It plays a key role in immune system regulation, contributes to the body's overall resistance to infections, and is involved in the production of antibodies to combat viruses and bacteria. Liver diseases are among the most prevalent health conditions worldwide, and their significance has become even more pronounced in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as highlighted by the World Health Organization on February 11, 2020.

Keywords: lymphocytes, clinic, mutation, coronavirus, COVID-19, chronic hepatitis, immunity.

Introduction: At the end of 2019, a previously unknown form of pneumonia emerged in the People's Republic of China, drawing global attention. It was soon identified as being caused by a novel coronavirus — SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2). On February 11, 2020, the World Health Organization officially named the disease caused by this virus *COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019)*. Pneumonia remains the primary clinical manifestation of COVID-19.

As the COVID-19 pandemic progressed and more clinical data became available, it became evident that the disease could present with symptoms beyond those typical of "atypical" pneumonia. Patients began to report neurological manifestations, skin changes, ocular lesions, and other extrapulmonary signs. Notably, the presence of SARS-CoV-2 was also detected in cholangiocytes, indicating the virus's ability to affect the liver.

Possible mechanisms of liver injury include direct viral cytopathic effects, systemic inflammation (such as cytokine storm), hypoxia, hypovolemia, hypotension during shock, and drug-induced hepatotoxicity. Biochemical abnormalities in liver function tests are observed in 14–53% of COVID-19 patients, although these changes are typically mild and do not require specific treatment. Acute hepatitis is rare.

However, special attention should be given to high-risk groups, including patients who have undergone liver transplantation and are receiving immunosuppressive therapy, those with decompensated cirrhosis, acute-on-chronic liver failure, hepatocellular carcinoma, or those undergoing antiviral treatment. Continuous data sharing, access to scientific developments, and the regular updating of clinical guidelines are crucial for effective management and improved outcomes in these patients.

Coronaviruses are widespread in nature and are responsible for up to 25% of common colds. Most coronaviruses cause mild viral infections that do not lead to significant health complications, but some, such as SARS-CoV (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus) and MERS-CoV (Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus), can lead to severe respiratory illness with high mortality rates. In nature, many species of bats serve as natural hosts for coronaviruses. These viruses evolve through mutations and preadaptation processes, periodically causing epidemics in human populations. For example, the outbreak of an unknown pneumonia in late December 2019

in China led to a public health emergency, eventually developing into a pandemic caused by the new SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus. On February 11, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) officially named the infection caused by the new virus as SARS-CoV-2 and the disease as COVID-19 ("CoronaVirus Disease 2019"). The mortality rate of this infection ranges from 0.5% to 3%.

SARS-CoV-2 is a zoonotic virus, closely related to a bat coronavirus strain (BM48-31/BGR/2008) with a 96% genetic identity. Bats appear to be the primary reservoir, and other mammals, including pangolins, may act as intermediate hosts, possibly transmitting the virus to humans. Phylogenetic analysis also shows that SARS-CoV-2 shares about 88% genetic similarity with SARS-CoV and around 50% with MERS-CoV.

The structure of coronaviruses causing respiratory syndromes is similar, and among the structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2 are the spike (S) protein, the membrane protein, and the nucleocapsid protein. The S-protein plays a key role in the virus's attachment to and penetration of host cells, making it a target for antibody production and vaccine development. The pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 infection is still being studied, but a key virulence factor is the interaction between the S-protein's receptor-binding domain (RBD) and the ACE2 receptor on human cells. This interaction is facilitated by the enzyme TMPRSS2, which activates the spike protein, allowing viral entry.

ACE2 is expressed in type II alveolar cells in the lungs, and it plays a protective role by maintaining surfactant levels. However, the binding of SARS-CoV-2 to ACE2 reduces its protective function, increasing the risk of infection. Notably, increased ACE2 expression does not rule out the possibility of stronger viral binding. ACE2 and TMPRSS2 expression levels vary among individuals of different genetic backgrounds, which may influence the severity of the infection.

Recent studies suggest that SARS-CoV-2 may also modify hemoglobin structure in erythrocytes, impairing oxygen transport and contributing to oxidative stress, hypoxia, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). However, this hypothesis remains to be confirmed through further research. Active viral replication in goblet cells, which are responsible for mucus production, may also facilitate virus entry and promote infection.

The immune response to SARS-CoV-2 infection often leads to a "cytokine storm," characterized by excessive production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-1 β , IL-6, and tumor necrosis factor. This overreaction, combined with reduced T-lymphocyte counts, exacerbates inflammation. Additionally, SARS-CoV-2 infects blood vessel endothelial cells, leading to endothelial dysfunction, microcirculatory disturbances, and thrombosis.

Histologically, lung tissue in COVID-19 patients shows evidence of diffuse alveolar damage, hyaline membrane formation, pulmonary edema, and fibrosis. Autopsy findings include mononuclear inflammatory infiltrates, fibrin microthrombi, and macrophages with viral inclusions. Severe cases exhibit hemorrhagic infarction and necrosis.

COVID-19 transmission primarily occurs through respiratory droplets from coughing, sneezing, or talking, and it can also spread via contact with contaminated surfaces or fecal-oral routes. The incubation period ranges from 2 to 14 days, with an average of 5-6 days. Individuals with cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, diabetes, and cancer are particularly vulnerable to severe COVID-19 outcomes.

The virus is highly contagious, with each infected person potentially transmitting it to 3-5 others. In contrast, the flu typically results in 1-2 secondary infections per patient. Importantly, some patients who have recovered from COVID-19 may continue to shed SARS-CoV-2 RNA even after clinical symptoms have resolved.

Ongoing research is exploring the effectiveness of experimental treatments for COVID-19, but definitive evidence remains scarce. Drug interactions, particularly among patients with pre-existing conditions, are an important consideration in clinical practice. The University of Liverpool provides an online resource to track drug interactions related to COVID-19 treatment.

Conclusion:

There have been over 3.5 million confirmed cases of COVID-19 worldwide, resulting in more than 250,000 deaths. Unfortunately, no specific, effective treatments for COVID-19 have been identified as of now. Numerous randomized clinical trials of various drugs are underway. To date, there is no conclusive evidence to suggest that patients who have recovered from COVID-19 are immune to re-infection.

It is essential to monitor individuals with antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 and compare them with those without, evaluating the frequency of re-infection and the potential development of COVID-19 over an extended period (at least one year).

However, early experimental use of plasma containing immunoglobulin G antibodies from recovered COVID-19 patients has shown promising results. Recovered patients, as well as asymptomatic individuals who continue to shed the virus in their feces, may pose a potential source of infection. Moreover, since SARS-CoV-2 RNA has been detected in wastewater samples, the viability of the virus in such environments — potentially facilitating fecal-oral transmission — remains an unresolved issue.

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